

**COGNITIVE- PRAGMATIC FEATURES OF THE EXPRESSIVE MEANS OF 'FUN' IN
ENGLISH AND UZBEK FICTIONAL AND CINEMATOGRAPHIC WORKS (IN THE EXAMPLE
OF 'TOSHBOLTA OSHIQ' BY HAMID GULAM AND 'WATCHMAN' BY ALAN MOORE)**

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ABSTRACT: This article is dedicated to the humour and irony in cognitive pragmatics. It also points out several features of cognitive pragmatics, humour and irony. Collected data was prepared on the basis of the work "Watchmen" by Alan Moore and on the book "Cognitive pragmatics " by Hans Jörg Schmid

Key words: Cognitive pragmatics, irony, humour, linguistic, social, creativity, artistic, phenomenon.

Ever since the publication of Arthur Koestler's early cognitive approach to humour in *The Act of Creation* (1964/1989), in which he inquires into the common cognitive grounds of highly disparate phenomena such as humour, artistic creativity and scientific discovery, cognitive psychologists and linguists have explored the cognitive mechanisms underlying humour and irony. The motivations for inquiring into the cognitive and inferential build-up of these two interrelated phenomena are manifold: (a) humour and irony are prominent types of linguistic creativity and for that reason alone deserve systematic scrutiny (the ecological validity argument, Graesser, Long, and Mio 1989; Tannen 1989; Glenn 2003), (b) they are complex cognitive phenomena on the interface between linguistic, cognitive, social, cultural, emotional and bodily factors, making them prime cases for interdisciplinary research (Goldstein 1990; Coulson 2000), and (c) they often build the playground for the 'fluid' conceptual system (Hofstadter 1995). Humour and irony have aroused interest in a variety of fields, ranging from philosophy to sociology and neuroscience. The multitude of theories and views that have emanated from the attempts to get to the essence of the phenomena are generally divided into three major categories: the cognitive theories that give a central role to incongruity and its resolution, social theories that highlight the importance of aggression, disparagement and the confirmation of superiority in

humour, and the tension-release models that find their origin in Sigmund Freud's early theory of the joke. Linguistic studies generally adopt an incongruity(resolution) perspective. Ever since the publication of Victor Raskin's seminal work on the Semantic Mechanisms of Humor (1985), linguistic humour research has had a decidedly cognitive orientation, and the cognitive psychological roots of the Semantic Script Theory of Humor (SSTH, cf. 2.1.) have been adopted in a large number of studies. The specific case of irony has remained on the agenda of (cognitive) pragmatics ever since Grice's discussion of the phenomenon as a specific case of the violation of conversational maxims. This has generated a range of theories that have been tested extensively in psycholinguistic and neurolinguistic experiments Over the past two decades, a number of overviews have been published tha discuss the main findings in linguistic and cognitive-psychological humour andr ony research (Attardo 1994, 2001a, 2005; Giora 2003; Raskin 2008; Gibbs and Colston 2007). Given these excellent surveys, this chapter takes a more restricted focus in the sense that it presents an overview of the contribution of Cognitive Linguistics (henceforth CL) to the study of humour and irony. Cognitive Linguistics, with its focus on the conceptual aspects of language use, provides an adequate framework for the analysis of the interplay of quantitative and qualitative aspects in humour and irony. However, for a long time both phenomena have been a largely unexamined topic in the cognitive linguistic paradigm, in contrast to the study of other instances of 'creative' and non-literal language use (like metaphor, metonymy, conceptual blending, etc.). Only since the turn of the century has CL developed an interest in humour as an additional research topic. The present chapter aims to present an exhaustive overview of this programme in cognitive pragmatics, with an explicit focus on the contribution of a CL approach to the larger field of linguistic humour and irony research. While irony and humour are not generally considered to be strictly distinguishable categories, the dichotomy will serve to structure the chapter. The first part deals with cognitive and pragmatic mechanisms of meaning construction in humour. I present the basic architecture of the two most influential linguistic humour theories, the Semantic Script Theory of Humor (SSTH, 2.1.) and the General Theory of Verbal Humor (GTVH, 2.2.). In 2.3., I discuss the contribution of Cognitive Linguistics to linguistic humour research, both from the perspective of its main proponents Rachel Giora (2.3.1.) and Seana Coulson (2.3.2) and in terms of key topics (2.3.3.) The second part of the

chapter provides a concise overview of cognitive pragmatic theories of irony. Following Attardo's (2000) excellent survey, I first present an outline of the two major groups of theories, viz. those that view irony as a figure of speech (3.1.), and those that take indirect echoing and mentioning as key features (3.2.). In 3.3., the few existing cognitive linguistic accounts of irony and sarcasm, situated within the framework of mental spaces theory, are discussed against the background of the main theories in the field. The chapter is closed off with some suggestions for future research on humour and irony in cognitive pragmatics.

Cognitive approaches to verbal humour The publication of Victor Raskin's *Semantic Mechanisms of Humor* (1985) marks the beginning of a strong linguistic tradition in humour research, with a decidedly cognitive orientation. Although this seminal work sets out to develop a competence theory of humour in the generative-linguistic tradition, hence pursuing a formal linguistic model that specifies the necessary and sufficient conditions for a text to be categorized as humorous, Raskin's actual proposal shares a number of basic assumptions with CL. In specifying his conception of a viable semantic theory, Raskin rejects a formal semantic view like that of Katz and Fodor (1963) in favour of a stronger contextual semantics that hinges on the notion of semantic scripts (Minsky 1975; Schank and Abelson 1977; and many others, cf. Kecskes, this volume). A script is defined as "a large chunk of semantic information surrounding the word or evoked by it. The script is a cognitive structure internalized by the native speaker and it represents the native speaker's knowledge of a small part of the world" (Raskin 1985: 81). Scripts thus are broadly compatible with frames (Fillmore 1982, 1985), domains (Lakoff and Johnson 1980; Langacker 1999) and Idealized Cognitive Models (ICMs, Lakoff 1987), which are more generally used in CL. In comparison to the latter, however, Raskin stresses that scripts are strongly tied to lexical elements, so that "every script is a graph with lexical nodes and semantic links between the nodes" (1985: 81). Cognitive linguists generally assume a less structurally bound perspective on frames (Coulson 2000, 2006; cf. 2.3.2.). Raskin's competence theory of verbal humour is dubbed the Semantic Script Theory of Humor (SSTH). The main hypothesis of the theory is described in terms of two conditions which must be satisfied for a text to be characterized as a 'singlejoke-carrying text': (i) The text is compatible, fully or in part, with two different scripts (ii) The two

scripts with which the text is compatible are opposite (Raskin 1985: 99) It should be noted that the theory takes the standard joke type with a punch line as the prototypical instance of verbal humour. For analytical reasons, Raskin restricts the scope of his model to that particular subcategory (Raskin 1985: 45–46) but stresses that in principle his theory is applicable to longer text types (see however Attardo 2001a and 2.2.2. below). The basic tenets of the theory can be illustrated using the stock example in (1), analyzed in great detail and from different perspectives over the last two decades: (1) “Is the doctor at home?” the patient asked in his bronchial whisper. “No,” the doctor’s young and pretty wife whispered in reply. “Come right in.” When conceived in a linear fashion, the text up to the punch line contains a number of lexical elements (doctor, patient, bronchial) that jointly activate the salient script of a (visit to the) DOCTOR. The punch line, however, seems at odds with the initial script-based interpretation, which leaves the reader or hearer with a semantic-pragmatic puzzle. According to the SSTH, this incongruity forces a pragmatic reorientation: the reader/hearer concludes that the normal bona fide pragmatic mode of communication, based on Grice’s principle of cooperation, does not hold for this particular piece of discourse. Rather, on the basis of the violation of (some of the) Gricean maxims, the reader/hearer assumes an alternative non-bonafide mode of communication, which is guided by conventions and knowledge of humorous texts (Raskin 1985: 100). Part of this knowledge is the overlap and opposition of semantic scripts as defined in the competence theory of the SSTH. Once the alternative communicative mode has been adopted, the hearer/reader can search for an alternative script-based interpretation that is compatible with the entire text. In the case of (1), elements like young, pretty and whispered, in combination with the information from the punch line of the joke, allow for the activation of the script of LOVE, and more specifically ADULTERY. The possibility of adopting an alternative script refers to the first aspect of Raskin’s definition quoted above: the text is partly or fully compatible with two different scripts. The reference to ‘different’ scripts pertains to the second aspect of the definition, viz. the relation between the two scripts. According to the SSTH, the two scripts should be opposite within the context of the joke. Oppositeness is defined in terms of a local antonymy: “two linguistic entities whose meanings are opposites only within a particular discourse and solely for the purposes of that discourse” (Raskin 1985: 108). In the scene described in (1), there is an obvious opposition between the scripts

DOCTOR and ADULTERY (with their different event structure and finality). The dynamic unfolding of script-based interpretations as language users process jokes is aptly termed script-switching (Raskin 1985) or frame-shifting (Coulson 2000): speakers/hearers switch from an initial salient script interpretation to a secondary construal that is compatible with the punch line and which is in a relationship of (local) opposition to the initial script. The switch is typically elicited by a specific textual element or segment, referred to as the semantic script-switch trigger (or disjunctor, Attardo 1994: 95). In the case of (1) the trigger coincides with the wife's reply ("come right in"). Script-switch triggers need to be distinguished from so-called connectors (Attardo 1994: 96), which are defined as the elements in the set-up of the text that are compatible with multiple script interpretations. Connectors thus are ambiguous elements that – in retrospect – put the reader/hearer on the wrong interpretational track before reaching the punch line. In (1), most notably the patient's question ("Is the doctor at home?") serves as a connector, because it is ambiguous as to what its pragmatic force is. Apart from pragmatically ambiguous text segments, jokes can obviously also revolve around (lexical) semantic ambiguity, as in the case of the polysemous strike in (2) and the idiomatic expression in (3):

(2) The first thing which strikes a stranger in New York is a big car. (Raskin 1985:26)

(3) I decided to start saving for a rainy day, so I went to a savings and loan and deposited my umbrella. (Giora 2003: 173)

It is generally assumed that the SSTH is the first systematic linguistic attempt at a formal theory with clearly defined and empirically testable hypotheses. As a consequence, virtually all studies on linguistic aspects of verbal humour since 1985 more or less explicitly relate to Raskin's foundational work. From the perspective of CL, the epistemological basis of the SSTH constitutes a direct link with the contextual semantics advocated in CL. Through its script-theoretic roots the SSTH adopts a non-reductionist view that is essential in order to account for complex semantic-pragmatic reinterpretation processes involved in joke processing. Raskin's basic theoretical claim on script-switching has been picked up in CL, most notably so in the empirical work by Coulson (2.3.2). Vaid et al. (2003) focus on the temporal discourse dynamics of the (re)interpretation process and provide evidence for a sudden shift in the priming of different script-based meanings. The results of these empirical studies are generally in support of the script-switching hypothesis, at least for the circumscribed subphenomenon of one-liner punch line jokes. The selection of the specific

genre of a single-joke-carrying text allowed Raskin to formalize his theory, in the hope that its insights would be scalable to the larger phenomenon of verbal humour (cf. Brône, Feyaerts, and Veale 2006: 224–226). As a consequence, the focus of the SSTH is restricted to a single semantic phenomenon while other relevant linguistic parameters, including phonetic patterning, genre knowledge, sociolinguistic variables, etc., are excluded from the analysis. Hence the granularity of an SSTH analysis is necessarily coarse, as it consists of listing lexically activated scripts and how they are combined to build a coherent interpretation. The output is a highly schematic, almost “semic dichotomy” (Vandaele 2002: 223) between abstract scripts, which was often criticized as reducing the complexity of the phenomenon (Dolitsky 1986; Mulkay 1988; Giora 1991; Martin 2007). These criticisms of reductionism led to the development of a revised theory on the epistemological foundations of the SSTH, the so-called General Theory of Verbal Humor (GTVH, Attardo and Raskin 1991; Attardo 1994, 2001a)

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